

ASSESSMENT OF GROUNDWATER QUALITY AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISKS FOR DRINKING PURPOSES IN MULTAN AND BAHAWALPUR CITY A STUDY FROM LINCOLN UNIVERSITY COLLEGE MALAYSIA

Mahlab Ijaz^{*1}, Suriyakla Perumal Chandran², Muhammad Ali³

^{*1}Phd Scholar (Phd in Health Sciences Specialized in Public Health) Faculty of Medicine, Lincoln University College Malaysia

²Associate Professor Biochemistry and Genetics Unit Deputy Dean Md-Pre-Clinical, Faculty of Medicine, Lincoln University College Malaysia

³Assistant Professor Department of Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture, Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

^{*1}mahlabijaz15@Gmail.Com, ²suriyakaka@Lincoln.Edu.My, ³muhammadali@Iub.Edu.Pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948250>

Keywords

Ground water quality, health risk, Heavy metals, cancer risk

Article History

Received: 28 April, 2025

Accepted: 05 July, 2025

Published: 26 August, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Mahlab Ijaz

Abstract

In rural and suburban areas, people unknowingly use poor ground water without understanding the full-scale negative impact on their health. Multan and Bahawalpur are two major cities in Southern Punjab. Ground water quality of both cities is degenerating with the passage of time. Therefore, distribution of ions, ground water quality, heavy metal occurrence and health risk assessment is to be studied. For this fifty ground water samples were taken from different localities of both cities. EC and TDS of both cities were high enough to make unfit for any purpose. Cations and anions were within limits as suggested by WHO except bicarbonates and sulphates ion which are slightly above in some water samples. Heavy metal concentration (As, Cd, Cr, Fe) in all water samples were high enough to make water hazardous. Water quality index and heavy metal pollution index ranked ground water of both cities from poor to hazardous. Chronic daily intake (CDI) and hazard quotient (HQ) for both age groups varied significantly. HQ in most of the ground water samples of Multan exceeded by 1 for adult age group making it potential carcinogenic for health. Among all heavy metals, arsenic gives potential cancer risk for both age groups. Therefore, it is the need of hour to install ground water purification system in the sampled area for effective management, monitoring and to protect local community from potential illness. Responsive actions must be taken to restore ground water quality by cutting off contamination sources including industrial effluents discharge, fertilizers and pesticides application

Introduction

Water is necessary to sustain life on earth. Around the globe only 3% fresh water is available of which 67% is captured by snow covered mountains, 30% in ground and 3% in the surface of the earth

(Hosseinia and Hassanzadeh, 2023). Ground water is a major reservoir of natural fresh water source and primary source of drinking water in many regions of the world. Vulnerability of

ground water resource towards pollutants depends upon the layer above the saturated zone which retains or neutralizes pollutant (Moldovan et al., 2020). Ground water is superior to surface water in terms of quality but it is influenced by anthropogenic process i.e., urbanization, intensive agricultural practices, industrial effluents & sanitation and natural process i.e., weathering and ground water recharge (Ullah et al., 2024). Degenerating ground water quality triggers various environmental and ecological issues which poses health risk to humans. An extensive study conducted by Adimalla (2019) on ground water quality of South India in arid to semi-arid condition reported potential health risk associated to consuming poor quality ground water for prolonged time.

Health risk assessment due to ground water quality has major implications on human health. Human health risk associated to ground water quality will contaminate by various sources i.e., industrial, domestic or agricultural site. Since ground water is the primary source used for drinking purpose its remediation is a challenging task then surface water resource like river, stream and lake (Pan et al., 2023). Drinking contaminated water on the other hand will also cause various diseases. High concentration of nitrate in drinking water may causes methemoglobinemia while high fluoride content may cause dental fluorosis (Shi et al., 2024). Ground water quality of Pakistan is deteriorating by various factors including industrial effluents, agricultural wastes and climate change. Ground water resources in arid to semi-arid regions are more prone to abovementioned factors with expediting health risk due to high consumption rate of poor quality ground water. Heavy metal toxicity is major factor behind increased human health risk. A study conducted by Waqas et al. (2017) suggest that high As concentration in ground water of Lahore resulted into high risk of As induced diseases due to increased chronic daily uptake through oral and dermal exposure.

Quality of ground water is important for public health as consuming tainted ground water might cause illness due to transmission of diseases. Persistence of heavy metal in ground water

resources for prolonged time in poorly managed urbanizes area of Punjab is a serious health hazard. Under such prevailing condition, current work is designed with an aim to quantify ground water characteristics of Multan and Bahawalpur City influenced by external factors. Water quality index (WQI), heavy metal pollution index (HPI) and health risk assessment were predicted to evaluate water for drinking purpose. Analyzed results gives essential insights into ground water quality with special reference to health risk assessment.

Materials and methods

Disruption of study area

Multan and Bahawalpur are two major cities of South Punjab, with an area of 3721 km² and 246 km², respectively. Multan (30.1864° N 71.4886° E) is an ancient city situated along river Chenab with inhabitant of 2.2 million while Bahawalpur (29.3544° N 71.6911° E) is situated along river Satluj with population of 0.9 million. Both cities were belongs to arid to semi-arid climatic zone with mean annual rainfall is 175 mm in Multan and 143 mm in Bahawalpur insufficient to alter ground water quality which is degenerating for decades due to industrial effluents and agricultural wastage. Annual rainfall is high in concentration between July and September during monsoon season. Temperature of both cities varied between 40°C and 5°C. Both rivers were flown seasonally in monsoon which is also insufficient to recharge ground water reservoirs. Inhabitant of both cities was dependent to ground water long ago as it is easy in term of access.

Field sampling and analytical procedure

Between May and June 2024 (pre monsoon dry season) fifty ground water samples (Five samples from each location at different coordinate within 500 meter and similar depth) were collected from each city. Water samples were kept in pre-cleaned polythene bags under 4°C prior to laboratory analysis. Field based portable equipment's were used to measure water temperature, pH and electrical conductivity. Water samples collected at the depth was recorded along with location of the sampling sites by using Global Positioning System (GPS) as given in table 1.

Collected ground water samples were physico-chemically analyzed for temperature, pH, EC, cationic and anionic concentration. Ordinary thermometer was used to measure the temperature of water. pH of water is determined by pH meter (Model: Mi-150) while electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS) ($TDS = EC \times 650$) was determined by EC meter (Model: 3100C). Prior to use both equipment's were pre-calibrated with potassium chloride solution. Cations (Na^+ , K^+

& Ca^{2+}) were determined by flame photometer (Model: BWB technologies). Mg^{2+} was determined by developing color in the solution and check absorbance in UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model: CE7400S). Anions (HCO_3^- , NO_3^- , F & Cl) was determined by titration method. Physico-chemical parameters were done according to the protocol of APHA (American Public Health Association) (Greenberg et al., 2005).

Table 1 indicates coordinates of water sample collecting sites in Multan and Bahawalpur

Multan		Bahawalpur	
Location	Coordinate	Location	Coordinate
Nawan Shehr	30.1961° N 71.4534° E	Maqbool colony	29.3775° N 71.7217° E
New Multan colony	30.2041° N 71.5144° E	Akbar colony	29.3928° N 71.7154° E
Jan Muhammad colony	30.2030° N 71.4920° E	Gharib Abad	29.4643° N 71.6411° E
Mohalla Qadirabad	30.1995° N 71.4610° E	Modal Town B	29.3966° N 71.6645° E
Basti Nau	30.2613° N 71.4838° E	Cheema Town	29.3947° N 71.6478° E

Water Quality Index (WQI)

Water quality index is an important mathematical tool to assess the composite influence of chemicals towards the water status which could alter the water quality. Following equations were subjected to extract out the WQI of specific water samples;

$$WQI = \sum_{i=1}^n Qi$$

Where; n = number of samples, i = parameter range and Qi = relative measure of water specific to each parameter.

Heavy metal Pollution Index (HPI)

All collected ground water samples were analyzed for heavy metals including As, Cd, Cr and Fe by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (Model: Shimadzu 7000F). Heavy metal pollution index is employed to identify cumulative effect of all metals on water quality. Following equation is used to establish heavy metal pollution index:

$$HPI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n WiQi}{\sum_{i=1}^n Wi}$$

Where; Qi is sub index calculated by following equation, Wi is unit weightage and n is the total number of samples.

$$Qi = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Mi - li}{Si - li} \times 100$$

Where; Mi is ith value of an element, li is ideal value and Si is the standard value.

Health Risk Assessment

Health risk assessment is applied to determine the non-carcinogenic health risk after consuming potentially inadequate water. Population was divided into two distinct age groups i.e., children (0-21 years) and adult (22-72 years). Human health risk was calculated by chronic daily intake for both age groups was computed by following equations;

$$CDI_{Oral} = \frac{C \times IR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT}$$

Where; C is the concentration of metal, IR is the ingestion rate (2.2 L day^{-1} for adult/ 1 L day^{-1} for children), EF is exposure frequency (365 days year⁻¹), ED is exposure duration (70 years for adult and

10 years for children), BW is the average body weight (70 kg for adult and 20 kg for children) and AT is average time of the exposure ($ED \times 365 = 25550$ days for an adult and 7300 days for children).

To calculate non-carcinogenic health risk, hazard quotient (HQ) was determined. HQ greater than 1 indicates non-carcinogenic health risk.

$$HQ = \frac{\text{Intake}}{\text{RfD}}$$

Where; RfD is reference dose ($\text{mg}/\text{kg}/\text{day}^{-1}$) which is 0.0003, 0.0005 and 0.003 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$ for As, Cd and Cr, respectively.

Life time cancer risk was measured by following equation;

$$\text{Cancer risk} = \text{Intake} \times \text{SF}$$

SF is slope factor which is 1.5 for As and 0.5 for Cr according to USEPA.

Results:

Physico-chemical properties of ground water samples

Physico-chemical properties of ground water samples as indicated in table 2a&b gives nature of ground water which is influenced by anthropogenic activities govern by environmental conditions of sampling area. Average pH of ground water samples was natural to slightly alkaline which indicates the seasonal variation between spring to summer. Electrical conductivity in few ground water samples of Multan is slightly above the threshold set by world health organization in terms of drinking purpose however ground water samples of Bahawalpur were not fall in the same category due to high salt concentration (up to $4560 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}^{-1}$). Total dissolved solids (TDS) in Multan is as high of $2291 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$ making it unfit for drinking. In case of water samples collected from Bahawalpur TDS is $4112 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$ which is twice as observed in the water samples collected from Multan. 40% ground water samples exhibited hardness level surpasses permissible limit as suggested by WHO in both selected study areas. Sulphates make the taste of

water as its higher concentration in water make the water bitter in taste. Only ground water samples in Bahawalpur collected from Maqbool colony gives bitter taste which is reinforced by SO_4^{2-} concentration ($998 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$). Bicarbonates in water samples is limited up to $500 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$ by WHO as beyond this limit it is harmful. Neither ground water sample from both cities' selected areas doesn't exhibit exceeded HCO_3^- concentration. Chloride, nitrate and fluoride ions in all water samples were also in the permissible limit ($200 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$ & $2 \text{ mg}/\text{L}^{-1}$ respectively) which might be regulated by ground water recharge under different environmental circumstances. All major cations (Mg, Na, K & Ca) were well under permissible limit according to the protocol developed by WHO.

Concentration of As, Cd, Cr and Fe were high enough to cause various diseases upon consumption. An increasing trend in all heavy metals was noticed in sampling areas of both cities. Among all arsenic is the most abundant heavy metal to be found in the water samples with its highest concentration of $11.65 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}^{-1}$. Followed by arsenic is chromium which is only deposited in the ground water samples taken from Multan while no traces were recorded in the water samples collected from Bahawalpur. Highest chromium content found to be at concentration of $5.53 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}^{-1}$ which might cause chronic to acute diseases. Since chromium in ground water is dependent to environmental variations which are not reported by other metals since they are governed by anthropogenic activities (As, Cd & Fe). Cadmium in ground water samples of both cities was slightly above as prescribed by WHO ($3 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}^{-1}$). Cadmium concentration even in trace form is lethal upon consumption. Iron concentration in sampling area also gives varied concentration with highest involvement through effluent discharge from the nearby industries. Highest Fe concentration was noted in the ground water samples taken from Jan Muhammad colony from Multan ($3.09 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}^{-1}$) and Gharib Abad in Bahawalpur ($3.39 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}^{-1}$).

Table 2 indicates physic-chemical properties of ground water samples taken from A) Multan & B) Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan

Sampling Sites A)	pH	EC ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	TDS (mg/L)	Hardne ss (mg/L)	SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	F ⁻ (mg /L)	HCO_3^- (mg/L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	NO_3^- (mg/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mg /L)	Na ⁺ (mg/L)	K ⁺ (mg /L)	Ca ²⁺ (mg /L)	As ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Fe ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cr ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
Nawan Shehr	7.29	2939	2277	559.8	164.41	1.32	294.9	88.2	0.88	17	59	2.97	34	10.32	3.0	2.88	3.43
New Multan colony	7.31	1561	1763	479.8	154.95	0.67	181.6	57.8	0.6	15	50.9	3.87	30	9.61	2.31	2.77	5.53
Jan Muhammad colony	7.88	2050	2086	430	115.49	0.58	165.3	87.3	0.83	26	123.6	5.01	62	11.65	3.29	3.09	3.36
Mohalla Qadirabad	7.76	1139	1112	150.4	65.29	0.37	128.3	118.6	0.55	12	40.6	4.06	40	8.33	2.64	2.33	3.89
Basti Nau	7.48	2456	2291	669.6	89.78	1.45	243	143.4	0.98	27	131.3	4.51	61	10.08	2.77	2.84	2.69
Maximum	7.88	2939	2291	669.6	164.42	1.45	294.9	143.4	0.98	27	131.3	5.01	62	11.65	3.29	3.09	5.53
Minimum	7.29	1139	1112	150.4	65.29	0.37	128.3	57.8	0.55	12	40.6	2.97	30	8.33	2.31	2.33	2.69
Mean	7.55	2029	1906	457.92	117.99	0.88	202.6	99.0	0.77	19.4	81	4.08	45.4	10.0	2.8	2.78	3.78
Standard Deviation	0.27	711.3	491.9	194.3	42.13	0.48	66.14	32.8	0.19	6.73	42.9	0.76	15.1	1.2	0.37	0.28	1.07
Coefficient Variation	of 3.53	35.05	25.81	42.43	35.71	54.5	32.64	33.13	24.23	34.6	52.9	18.6	33.3	11.99	13.18	9.98	28.24

Sampling Sites B)	pH	EC ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	TDS (mg/L)	Hardne ss (mg/L)	SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	F ⁻ (mg /L)	HCO_3^- (mg/L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	NO_3^- (mg/L)	Mg^{2+} (mg /L)	Na ⁺ (mg/L)	K ⁺ (mg /L)	Ca ²⁺ (mg /L)	As ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cd ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Fe ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Cr ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
Bahawalpur																	
Maqbool colony	7.32	4560	4112	720.2	998.04	1.52	456.8	134	0.99	23	91.4	7.26	58	7.65	2.26	2.56	0
Akbar colony	7.70	3510	3464	750	394.75	1.64	437.3	150.7	1.11	26	126.7	4.27	66	8.58	2.65	2.61	0
Gharib Abad	7.78	2916	2533	350.2	242.89	0.80	154.9	92.6	0.77	18	64.2	4.61	53	9.91	3.23	3.39	0
Modal Town B	7.80	1906	1701	250	220.77	0.25	132.7	85.1	0.62	13	50.8	5.06	49	8.11	2.67	2.01	0
Cheema Town	7.58	1718	1864	320.2	148.50	0.51	204.2	121.7	0.63	12	58.9	5.11	35	6.55	2.23	2.04	0
Maximum	7.80	4560	4112	750	998.04	1.64	456.8	150.7	1.11	26	126.7	7.26	66	9.91	3.23	3.39	0
Minimum	7.32	1718	1701	250	148.51	0.25	132.7	85.1	0.62	12	50.8	4.26	35	6.55	2.23	2.01	0
Mean	7.64	2922	2735	478.1	400.99	0.94	277.2	116.8	0.83	18.4	78.4	5.26	52.2	8.16	2.61	2.52	0
Standard Deviation	0.19	1173	1036	237.6	345.59	0.61	157.3	27.66	0.22	6.11	31	1.17	11.5	1.23	0.40	0.56	0
Coefficient of Variation	2.55	40.16	37.88	49.7	86.18	65.1	56.76	23.67	26.47	33.1	39.55	22.2	22	15.12	15.5	22.13	0

Water quality Indices

Water quality indices of water samples from both cities ranged between 82.4 and 263.8 indicating very poor to hazardous ground water quality. Only ground water from Mohalla Qadirabad in Multan indicates poor ground water quality while others were categorize in hazardous water quality. Highest WQI was noted in Maqbool colony (263.8), followed by Akbar colony (229.8) and Basti Nau (172.6) as given in figure 1.

Figure 1 indicating ground water quality index of water samples collected from various locations of A) Multan and B) Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan

Heavy metal pollution indices

Heavy metal pollution indices (HPI) are the cumulative concentrations of studied heavy metal i.e. As, Cd, Cr & Fe. HPI in the selected study areas ranges between 49 and 115 with good to hazardous heavy metal concentration. Least HPI was observed in Cheema town (49) in Bahawalpur. Highest HPI was noted in New Multan colony (115) followed by Jan Muhammad colony (108) and Nawan Shehr (103) as given in figure 2. Other ground water samples gives medium to high heavy metal pollution.

Figure 2 indicates heavy metal pollution index of As, Cd, Fe & Cr in ground water samples collected from different locations of A) Multan and B) Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan

**Health risk assessment
Non-carcinogenic risk**

Consuming contaminated water for long time cause potential health risks. Non-carcinogenic health risk followed by up taking contaminated water for long time is determined on the basis of average metal concentration in water sample. Table 3 and table 4 describe the chronic daily intake (CDI) which is much higher in both age groups. Calculated CDI in Multan is in the order of Fe > Cd > Cr > As while water samples collected

from Bahawalpur gives order as Cd > Fe > As. Similarly figure 3 indicates hazard quotient (HQ) which is also much higher in case of adult. HQ for adult in Multan is greater than 1 which is carcinogenic in terms of environmental and toxicological risk assessment. However HQ for child in both cities is less than 1 indicating its non-carcinogenic risk in this specific age group. Moreover, HQ for adult in water samples taken from Bahawalpur is also non-carcinogenic.

Table 3 indicates chronic daily intake through ingestion in different age groups of Multan city, Punjab, Pakistan

Sampling Sites	As		Cd		Cr		Fe	
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children
Nawan Shahr	0.00032	0.000025	0.000094	0.000075	0.000107	0.000085	0.000090	0.000072
New Multan colony	0.000302	0.00024	0.000072	0.00057	0.00017	0.00013	0.000087	0.000069
Jan Muhammad colony	0.00037	0.000029	0.000103	0.000082	0.000105	0.000084	0.000097	0.000077
Mohalla Qadirabad	0.00026	0.0002	0.000082	0.000066	0.000122	0.000097	0.000073	0.000058
Basti Nau	0.00032	0.000025	0.000087	0.000069	0.000084	0.000067	0.000089	0.000071

Table 4 indicates chronic daily intake through ingestion in different age groups of Bahawalpur city, Punjab, Pakistan

Sampling Sites	As		Cd		Fe	
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children
Maqbool colony	0.00024	0.00019	0.000071	0.000056	0.000080	0.000072
Akbar colony	0.00027	0.00021	0.000083	0.000066	0.000082	0.000069
Gharib Abad	0.00028	0.00025	0.00010	0.000080	0.00010	0.000077
Model Town B	0.00025	0.00020	0.000083	0.000066	0.000063	0.000058
Cheema Town	0.00021	0.00016	0.000070	0.000055	0.000064	0.000071

Figure 3 gives hazard quotient of both age groups by consuming ground water samples from different areas of Multan and Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan. A) Adult in Multan, B) Adult in Bahawalpur, C) Children in Multan, D) Children in Bahawalpur, As: Arsenic, Cd: Cadmium, Cr: Chromium, Fe: Iron

Cancer risk

Cancer risk for arsenic and chromium in both cities were given in table 5. WHO recommends safe limit of cancer risk is 1 in 1,000,000 lifetimes. In Multan across all sites, Nawan Shehr, Jan Muhammad colony, Basti Nau and New Multan colony exhibit highest arsenic/chromium level making it most at risk location in terms of potential cancer development by ingesting ground water while in Bahawalpur Gharib Abad exhibit highest cancer risk in terms of arsenic. Both age groups have potential cancer risk but children with higher ingestion intake to body ratio made it vulnerable to toxins during body development.

Table 5 indicates life time cancer risk of human health exposed to drinking water in Multan and Bahawalpur city, Punjab, Pakistan

Sampling Sites	As		Cr		As	Adult	Children
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children			
Nawan Shahr	0.000021	0.000017	0.00021	0.00017	Maqbool colony	0.00016	0.00012
New colony Multan	0.00002	0.00016	0.00034	0.00027	Akbar colony	0.00017	0.00014

Jan Muhammad colony	0.000024	0.000019	0.00021	0.00016	Gharib Abad	0.0002	0.00016
Mohalla Qadirabad	0.00017	0.00013	0.00024	0.00019	Modal Town B	0.00016	0.00013
Basti Nau	0.000021	0.000016	0.00016	0.00013	Cheema Town	0.00013	0.00019

Discussion

Ground water is of immense importance since it is the only natural undisturbed reservoir available to us. Furthermore ground water is the only source of available water to inhabitant in arid to semi-arid regions. In the current work sampling areas of both cities lies in arid condition with harsh environmental condition therefore ground water usage is the only option. pH of overall water sample is natural to slightly alkaline in nature which indicates the presence of carbonaceous rocks along water bodies which added bicarbonates into water through weathering process. Elevated level of electrical conductivity is present in overall water samples indicates presence of salts in large concentration which is harmful upon consumption. Further, total dissolved solids is evenly distributed in the overall water samples throughout both cities which is attributed to ion exchange between soil solids and soil liquid giving increased EC and TDS level in water (Kurakalva et al., 2021). Another possible reason behind enhanced EC and TDS is arid climatic conditions of area where sandy nature of soil helps percolate industrial effluents directly into the ground water reservoir without any infiltration process (Hassan et al., 2019). Ground water hardness is due to the accumulation of calcium carbonate rocks as water reservoir is covered by these rocks. Mohsin et al. (2013) describes that calcium and carbonates ion in dissolved form is the sole responsible of water hardness.

Tested cations and anions in water sample were within the range acceptable for drinking purpose according to WHO. It is worth noted that elevation in these cations and anions will be attributed to the domestic wastage, overuse of agricultural chemicals, pesticides and intensive agricultural practices. Bicarbonates accumulation in water sample even in controlled from is due to the weathering of carbonaceous rocks (Li et al.,

2019). Nitrate ions elevation is due to the increased use of pesticides containing derivatives of nitrates. This process is common in arable areas of Punjab where intensive agricultural practices after large use of nitrates also increase its concentration in ground water (Akhtar et al., 2021). Moderate level of sulphate, chloride and fluoride ions were present in ground water samples I due to the movement of water within the soil. Cations presence in ground water is similar to that of anions where only potassium is fixed with soil particles and slowly released into water. Other major cations like calcium, magnesium and sodium enter into ground water through infiltration of soluble salts, landfill leachates and industrial effluents (Jehan et al. 2023). Water quality index was executed to check the overall ground water quality giving hazardous nature of water in all samples. Poor ground water quality is associated to the presence of nearby rocks which influence water quality (Su et al., 2020).

Heavy metal distribution in studied area is assessed for its enrichment in ground water. Among all (As, Cd, Cr & Fe), arsenic is highly enriched in ground water of studied area due to due to the presence of nearby aluminum, iron and manganese which also helps increase pH of water. Presence of cadmium, chromium and iron in water samples mainly derived through anthropogenic activities like industrial effluents, agricultural inputs and transportation of weathered material (Wang et al., 2020). Heavy metal pollution index indicates cumulative concentration of heavy metal in ground water where few samples in Multan give hazardous nature of water then Bahawalpur ground water samples. It was noted that increased use of agrochemicals and pesticides increases heavy metal in water (NFDC, 2016).

Non-carcinogenic risk associated to consumption of water containing heavy metal gives increasing

hazard quotient trend for arsenic in water samples for adult age group. HQ greater than 1 is carcinogenic compared to less than 1 which is non-carcinogenic for human health. Alves et al. (2014) describes that anthropogenic activity is behind the increased HQ especially for As. On the other hand cadmium, chromium and iron are designated as non-carcinogenic for both age groups. Main reason behind increasing potential risk is increased water uptake as study area lies in arid climatic condition with relatively high humidity thus daily water average intake also increases. Cancer risk due to prolonged exposure to low concentration of heavy metal could also increase. Results regarding potential cancer risk due to up taking hazardous water are supported by the work of Wongsasuluk et al. (2014) suggesting high ground water consumption ratio to body weight poses cancer risk after long time. Results regarding cancer risk are also in accordance with the work of Cao et al. (2014) where high cancer risk is detrimental to human health.

Conclusion:

A study was conducted to evaluate ground water quality, heavy metal concentration and related health risk assessment in two major cities (Multan & Bahawalpur) of southern Punjab, Pakistan. Hydrochemical analysis of ground water revealed that major cations and anions found in water is influenced by rock-water interaction. High salt content along with dissolved solids is due to environmental condition of the local area. Water quality index and heavy metal pollution index surpasses the permissible limit in most of the sampled water and is hazardous when consumed for long time. It was also noted that heavy metal in the studied area is not evenly distributed as ground water is only degraded by industrial effluents in specific area. Carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risk assessment was computed by ingesting ground water. Hazard quotient reveals that adult in Multan are most vulnerable to potential health risk. Highest score in risk assessment was given by As followed by Cd, Cr and Fe. It was also noted that among all heavy metals, arsenic gives the highest chance of risk assessment. Current work provides an insight into the water quality and related health risk of two major cities in Southern Punjab.

Health risk assessment also clarifies that drinking polluted water for long time also affects human health and life style of local community.

REFERENCES

- Adimalla, N. (2019). Groundwater quality for drinking and irrigation purposes and potential health risks assessment: a case study from semi-arid region of South India. *Exposure and health*, 11(2), 109-123.
- Akhtar, N., Syakir Ishak, M. I., Bhawani, S. A. and Umar, K. (2021), Various natural and anthropogenic factors responsible for water quality degradation: A review, *Water*, 13, 2660.
- Alves, R. I., Sampaio, C. F., Nadal, M., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J. L. and Segura-Muñoz, S. I. (2014), Metal concentrations in surface water and sediments from Pardo River, Brazil: human health risks, *Environmental research*, 133, 149-155.
- Cao, S., Duan, X., Zhao, X., Ma, J., Dong, T., Huang, N., Sun, C., He, B. and Wei, F. (2014), Health risks from the exposure of children to As, Se, Pb and other heavy metals near the largest coking plant in China, *Science of the total environment*, 472, 1001-1009.
- Hassan, S. H., Gurung, A., Kang, W. C., Shin, B. S., Rahimnejad, M., Jeon, B. H., ... & Oh, S. E. (2019). Real-time monitoring of water quality of stream water using sulfur-oxidizing bacteria as bio-indicator. *Chemosphere*, 223, 58-63.
- Hosseini, M., & Hassanzadeh, R. (2023). Groundwater quality assessment for domestic and agricultural purposes using GIS, hydrochemical facies and water quality indices: case study of Rafsanjan plain, Kerman province, Iran. *Applied Water Science*, 13(3), 84.

- Jehan, S., Khattak, S. A., Khan, S., Ali, L. and Hussain, M. L. (2023), Hydrochemical evaluation of groundwater for drinking and irrigation purposes using multivariate indices along Indus Suture Zone, North Pakistan, *Environmental Geochemistry and Health*, 45 (5), 2511-2531.
- Kurakalva, R. M., Kuna, G., Vaiphei, S. P. and Guddeti, S. S. (2021), Evaluation of hydrogeochemical profile, potential health risk and groundwater quality in rapidly growing urban region of Hyderabad, South India, *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 80 (10), 383.
- Li, H., Wang, S., Bai, X., Cao, Y. and Wu, L. (2019), Spatiotemporal evolution of carbon sequestration of limestone weathering in China, *Science China Earth Sciences*, 62, 974-991.
- Mohsin, M., Safdar, S., Asghar, F. and Jamal, F. (2013), Assessment of drinking water quality and its impact on residents health in Bahawalpur city, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3 (15), 114-128.
- Moldovan, A., Hoaghia, M. A., Kovacs, E., Mirea, I. C., Kenesz, M., Arghir, R. A., ... & Moldovan, O. T. (2020). Quality and health risk assessment associated with water consumption—A case study on karstic springs. *Water*, 12(12), 3510.
- NFDC (2016) *Fertilizer Review, 2015-16*. Islamabad, Pakistan: Nat. Fert. Dev. Centre
- Pan, Y., Peng, H., Hou, Q., Peng, K., Shi, H., Wang, S., ... & Pi, P. (2023). Priority control factors for heavy metal groundwater contamination in peninsula regions based on source-oriented health risk assessment. *Science of The Total Environment*, 894, 165062.
- Shi, H., Du, Y., Xiong, Y., Deng, Y., & Li, Q. (2024). Source-oriented health risk assessment of groundwater nitrate by using EMMTE coupled with HHRA model. *Science of the Total Environment*, 934, 173283.
- Su, Z., Wu, J., He, X. and Elumalai, V. (2020), Temporal changes of groundwater quality within the groundwater depression cone and prediction of confined groundwater salinity using Grey Markov model in Yinchuan area of northwest China, *Exposure and Health*, 12 (3), 447-468.
- Ullah, A., Hussain, S., Wang, Y., Awais, M., Sajjad, M. M., Ejaz, N., Javed, U., ... & Iqbal, J. (2024). Integrated assessment of groundwater quality dynamics and Land use/land cover changes in rapidly urbanizing semi-arid region. *Environmental Research*, 260, 119622.
- Wang, Y., Duan, X. and Wang, L. (2020), Spatial distribution and source analysis of heavy metals in soils influenced by industrial enterprise distribution: Case study in Jiangsu Province, *Science of the Total Environment*, 710, 134953.
- Wongsasuluk, P., Chotpantararat, S., Siri Wong, W. and Robson, M. (2014), Heavy metal contamination and human health risk assessment in drinking water from shallow groundwater wells in an agricultural area in Ubon Ratchathani province, Thailand, *Environmental geochemistry and health*, 36, 169-182.
- Waqas, H., Shan, A., Khan, Y. G., Nawaz, R., Rizwan, M., Rehman, M. S. U., ... & Jabeen, M. (2017). Human health risk assessment of arsenic in groundwater aquifers of Lahore, Pakistan. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 23(4), 836-850.